

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

A foreign language textbook as a tool for professionalizing a future linguist's language training

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Abstract

The today need to professionalize the language training of specialists in various spheres of activity is obvious. However, when training future linguists (teachers, translators, intercultural communication specialists), this principle is manifested in a more in-depth study of language and speech phenomena. Yet, modern textbooks for linguists are seldom focused on the future profession. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the possibilities of thesaurus-style organization of educational material and its integration into the educational process, which could ensure the necessary level of professionalization of future linguists' language training. A textbook for future teachers of a foreign language can serve a good example of that. The leading approaches to the study of the problem are integrated and empirical ones. The integrated approach allows us to take into account the context of professional training of specialists, based on interdisciplinary connections between language, linguistics, pedagogy and didactics. The empirical approach is justified by the fact that the recommendations formulated by the author of the paper rely on her practical experience in teaching a foreign language to various categories of linguists. The results of the study, presented as conclusions about the structure of a professionally oriented textbook for future linguists - foreign language teachers, its organization principles, the features of the selection and formulation of tasks, can be used in the creation of textbooks for future teachers of various foreign languages, as well as for specialists in other areas of professional activity.

Keywords linguists, professional thesaurus, professional language training, a foreign language textbook.

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Introduction

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The textbook is an indispensable tool in the learning process. Being influenced by society, science, and technology, its concept, content, and form may change, but its systemic function remains the same. A textbook for higher education plays a special role, since it participates in a complex multidimensional process of forming the students' professional personality while their success in the professional sphere depends on its quality. Let us consider the role of a foreign language textbook for future linguists, foreign language teachers in the formation of their professional self-awareness and readiness for teaching activities.

As L.G. Vikulova and her co-authors point out, the formation of a modern specialist's qualities and features should take place through all subjects (including a foreign language). The modern pedagogical community confirms this thesis (Vikulova et al., 2020, p.71). Consequently, in training future linguists, a foreign language should also develop not only the students' linguistic but also professional competencies. Many scientists (I.S. Alekseeva, N.N. Gavrilenko, E.R. Porshneva, T.S. Serova, I.I. Khaleeva, M.Y. Zvilling, Y. Gambier, D. Gouadec, E. Lavault, M. Lederer, and others) emphasize the importance of professionally directed language teaching, which contributes to the formation and development of the students' professional language personality.

However, paradoxically, the research on the organization of foreign language training for linguists is most often limited to the definition of the importance of better teaching and learning a foreign language, the need to develop communicative, intercultural and other competencies. At the same time, the idea of the need to teach and learn a foreign language from the perspective of future professional activity (translator, foreign language teacher or intercultural communication specialist) is pronounced much less often, especially in comparison with the language training of specialists. Nevertheless, this problem seems urgent in the light of modern requirements for the professional training of linguists. A practical solution of this problem is possible only through the creation of separate professionally oriented foreign language textbooks for specialists of each profile of the given training sphere.

Purpose and objectives of the study

Having determined the importance of professionalizing the language training of a foreign language teacher and choosing a foreign language textbook as a tool, we need to develop such a concept that, while maintaining the goal of developing foreign language communicative competence in its broadest meaning, will allow us to give this process a professional orientation. The solution to this problem will make it possible to transform the linguistic training of future teachers from courses of advanced study of a foreign language, where the expression "professional language proficiency" means a high level of language, into an

important stage of the conscious process of becoming a foreign language teacher, who sees his professionalism in the ability and willingness to teach this language.

Literature review

The stages of the formation of professionally oriented foreign language teaching have been analyzed in a paper by Olschvang (2019). The author notes that as an independent direction in foreign language teaching methodology, a vocation oriented foreign language teaching has been around for about 60 years, although the approach itself dates back several centuries (Olschvang, 2019, p. 217-218). The development of economic ties, scientific research, teaching, diplomatic contacts, and wars had a significant impact on the development of professionally oriented foreign language teaching. As professional linguistics evolved, so did the approaches to professionally oriented language teaching. Thus, at the beginning, the focus was on special vocabulary in technical and scientific texts, then the emphasis shifted to the rhetorical aspect of language in specific discourses, then the competence approach came to the fore, and nowadays, special attention is paid to the text genre; corpus studies have been introduced. Despite the possibility to trace the stages according to which this section of linguo-didactics developed, the author notes that the existing approaches are constantly being rethought and combined (Olschvang, 2019). As confirmation, let us cite the words of A.P. Minyar-Belorucheva, who believes that professionally oriented foreign language textbooks should, to some extent, reflect the results of research on each of the detected stages of professionally oriented foreign language teaching:

- 1) register analysis (professional language analysis);
- 2) discourse analysis;
- 3) target communicative situation analysis;
- 4) stage of skills and strategic ways of language acquisition;
- 5) learning- and learner-oriented approach (Minyar-Belorucheva, 2010, p. 97).

The works analyzed above clearly show that professionally oriented teaching of foreign languages is considered only in the context of language training of non-linguistic professionals.

This perspective is also applicable to the linguistic training of foreign language teachers whose professional sublanguage is the sublanguage of linguo-didactics and foreign language teaching methodology, the study of which is necessary to communicate with foreign colleagues and to read specialized literature. Among the

works devoted to this aspect of teachers' language training we can mention a dissertation research by Antyushina (2006) devoted to teaching foreign-language professional speech to a future foreign language teacher. However, professionalization of a foreign language learning process by a future teacher solely at one of the last training stages is clearly insufficient for the formation of his/her professional self-consciousness.

A.A. Kolesnikov speaks about the necessity to introduce a career guidance component into the integral process of continuous philological/linguistic education, including the stages of high school, linguistic/philological university, postgraduate education, explaining this need by the trends of informational and communicative society development (Kolesnikov, 2013). When speaking about a career-oriented foreign language teaching he means the orientation of the competences developed within the "Foreign Language" discipline and the associated disciplines of the linguistic and philological cycle (country studies, literature, stylistics, lexicology, etc) towards familiarizing both cognitively and practically with some aspects of different communicative-oriented professional areas. It is necessary to form ideas about the specificity of this or that professional activity on this basis and to assess one's capabilities and one's level of readiness for this profession (Kolesnikov, 2013). We believe that future linguists should begin professionally oriented learning within their linguistic education directly with the orientation towards their future professional activity.

The work by Golovchanskaya (2016) corresponds most of all to the professional focus of future foreign language teachers' linguistic training, but it is devoted only to one of the aspects of this training, namely, the formation of phono-stylistic competence within a separate discipline, not in the course of speech practice.

Thus, the question of the specifics of professionally directed foreign language training of future linguists - teachers of a foreign language in the scientific literature has not been fully covered. We assume that the problem is related to the complex status of a foreign language for this category of students, which acts both as an object of study and as a future subject of study, also as a means of receiving and transmitting information, as a tool of communication, including professional one. However, it seems to us that the problem can be solved with the help of a textbook, which, provided specially designed exercises and reformulation of some traditional tasks, is able to give the study of a foreign language a professional value-oriented character.

Methodology

The effectiveness of a textbook depends on how deeply the author recognized and articulated the

approaches and principles underlying it (Kravtsova & Yastrebova, p.49).

As E. G. Tareva and E. M. Kazantseva claim, the purpose of the textbook is the formation and development of professional competence of the graduate who is able to carry out professional activities, and willing to continue the education in various forms of postgraduate education and self-education (Tareva, 2011, p.70).

In our opinion, a foreign language textbook for future linguists-teachers should also strive to achieve this goal and must have a professional emphasis from the very beginning of their language training.

For a long time, the author of this paper has been studying the problem of professionalization of language training of linguists-future translators in the field of economics (Abdulmyanova, 2008). These studies have resulted in the development of a thesaurus method of teaching future translators an economic sublanguage. The idea of using this method, which has a great theoretical and practical potential in the professional training of any specialist, became the basis for the concept of the textbook "French for future teachers" which is being developed by the author at the moment. Its purpose is to develop the professional thesaurus of a foreign language teacher by means of a foreign language.

Taking advantage of the universality of the translator's thesaurus definition, we defined the professional thesaurus of a teacher as an open system that provides for the interrelated accumulation, storage, and multiplication of information, knowledge, and human experience. This system is the informational and conceptual basis for education, human activity, formation and development of an individual and society. The professional-pedagogical thesaurus is characterized by the presence of an integrative system of terms, knowledge, ideas, concepts in the sphere of pedagogy, psychology, the subject of specialization and methods of its teaching, as well as value-based attitude to this sphere and to the whole world in general through the prism of pedagogical activity (Abdulmyanova & Mikhailova, 2020, p. 7).

The main components of the teacher's professional thesaurus are interrelated and activated in the process of professional activity – when teaching the subject the teacher is guided by the teaching methodology. The professional thesaurus of a foreign language teacher has an even more complex structure due to its bilingualism (multilingualism) and biculturality (multiculturalism). Knowledge of a foreign language has an impact not only on the thesaurus of the specialty, but also on its other components, since a foreign language acts not only as an object of study and as a subject of training, but also as a means of obtaining and transmitting information. It promotes developing psychological, pedagogical, methodological and related thesauri through the study of foreign sources and professional interaction with colleagues from different countries. Thus, in the language training of future teachers of a foreign language, it is necessary to constantly remember the role of this process in the formation of their professional thesaurus. It is most

expedient to do this with the help of specially designed exercises and tasks that provide a thesaurus organization of knowledge with stable internal connections, systematized in the textbook with which they learn a foreign language.

Let us consider the conceptual foundations of the professionalization of the language training of future teachers of foreign languages basing on a textbook aimed at forming their professional thesaurus. It is obvious that this process, due to the complexity of the task, is multi-stage and depends not only on the progress in language acquisition, but also on the pace of students' progress in the study of linguistics, pedagogy, psychology and teaching methods. A textbook on a foreign language can not contain tasks for the development of exercises on a particular aspect until these competencies have been formed at the methodology lessons. Thus, the first principle of thesaurus formation by means of a foreign language textbook is the principle of consciousness. According to A.V. Shchepilova, there are two levels of consciousness: first, when consciousness in learning is understood as the student's intention (motivation), the desire to learn new things; understanding the goals and methods of assigning new knowledge, arbitrary attention; and second, when it is something like controlling one's speech actions in the process of mastering the linguistic phenomena in a foreign language (Shchepilova, 2005, p. 142).

Consciousness should be achieved in the study of language phenomena, tasks should contribute to the development of the ability to explain the use of each individual phenomenon; this skill will be one of the fundamental ones in future professional activities. At the initial stage, such tasks can be done in the native language, but as the thesaurus is replenished with terms and concepts from the field of linguistics and the transition to higher levels of language proficiency, the share of the native language will decrease. In addition, students should be aware of the pragmatic role of the tasks performed. Therefore, after training exercises and tasks that transform the studied phenomena into speech, it is necessary to provide problem tasks that simulate professional situations in which these phenomena will acquire a value-based meaning. Such exercises should be introduced from the very beginning of language learning. The second principle is the principle of spiral, or concentric, progression in the material assimilation, which ensures the strength of the material assimilation due to repeatability with its gradual complication. The complication in our case will manifest itself not only in the studied material complication, but also in the complication of the tasks that model the situations of pedagogical interaction.

Another principle that should be followed when creating the desired textbook is the principle of activity. From the perspective of constructivism and according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR, 2018), individuals are active protagonists in their learning process, creating their own knowledge (Relvas, 2020). Activity should be manifested both in involvement in speech activity, and

in the formation of a professional thesaurus. To do this, students should see their goal not only in mastering the language as a means of communication, but also as a subject that will need to be taught to others. Understanding the purpose of language training should change the motivation of future teachers when learning a language. They should realize the responsibility, while the proposed exercises and tasks will help them develop the necessary competencies and increase their readiness for professional activity.

To ensure the thesaurus organization of knowledge, we will use the strategy that we borrowed from Shchepilova's work (2005), supplementing it with professional values aimed at learning a foreign language.

Results

Structure of a lesson in a professionally-oriented foreign language textbook for future teachers

Having identified the main aspects of the future textbook, we offer the following structure and examples of statements that reflect its concept.

Each lesson begins with the studied topic definition and a suggestion to create subtopics, skills, and a list of words (in the native language at the initial stage, in the foreign language at a more advanced level. The students (hypothetical students) must learn these words in order to be able to communicate on this topic. Thus, students, determining the object, the subject of study, the necessary skills, actively participate in the tasks setting – the goal-setting stage.

At the next stage, students are asked to find foreign-language equivalents for the short-list without using dictionaries and to analyze their existing knowledge and gaps – the stage of activating the foreign-language personal thesaurus, which can be completed by drawing up a table or a mental map in a format that allows them to be filled in further.

Then comes the stage of familiarization with the language material and rules, the knowledge of which was determined at the goal-setting stage as necessary.

The study of authentic text material, accompanied by the analysis of the use of previously studied language material, the identification of linguo-culturological and socio-cultural features that should be paid attention to in order to understand and explain the text completes the process of getting acquainted with the new language material.

Conceptualization stage of new knowledge through communicative and professionally-oriented exercises and tasks attaches value to the material studied from the point of view of its use in the communication process,

including through the prism of the future profession.

The reproductive-productive stage helps to conduct training of the new knowledge usage in the simulated professional activity. Students are offered tasks that require explanations, comments, and assessments, including using fill-in tables and mental maps.

The final stage is the analysis of the contextual use of the studied words, grammatical phenomena using the example of additional texts for different categories of recipients (children, adolescents, adults, native speakers, persons learning a language as a foreign language).

Examples of phrasing that create a professional attitude to the foreign language mastering:

Most of the tasks used in modern foreign language textbooks can be focused professionally and communicatively. For example, it is quite logical to replace the traditional task of determining correct and incorrect judgments with the following: *Listen to/read the text and check the answers given by the students. Praise them for the correct answers and correct the wrong ones.* Such a task turns an ordinary task for text comprehension into a task with a professional communicative meaning. Its value for professional development is obvious.

Let's consider another task that is aimed at developing students' lexical skills (see Table 1).

Table 1.

Task for lexical skills development

<i>Word</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Synonyms</i>	<i>Antonyms</i>	<i>Context</i>
	<i>a feeling of worry and fear</i>			

Read the definition and search the text for the word, which means the same as this definition. Complete the table with the missing information.

This task contributes to the thesaurus-based organization of knowledge, but at the same time, in this version, it does not exhaust its potential to contribute to the formation of a professional thesaurus, since it lacks a value aspect. If you put it into a professional context, it will give it an additional professional meaning: *Based on the final table, explain the meaning of the new words in different ways to your hypothetical students.*

Such tasks can be offered when working out any lexical material and provide both high-quality mastery of the studied material and the formation of professional competencies.

Criteria of effectiveness

Based on the criteria for a foreign language textbook effectiveness presented in (Luis, 2020), we have developed a list of questions, the answers to which will determine the benefits and effectiveness of exercises and tasks in the development of a professional thesaurus using the developed textbook:

- The textbook materials and exercises are contemporary and applicable in professional pedagogical contexts
- The exercises for the students are applicable and useful for their future profession
- The textbook provides pronunciation, reading, writing, speaking, listening training and helps to analyse peculiarities of these skills important for the future profession from the beginning
- The textbook is well organized; its structure is useful for the pedagogical thesaurus development
- The textbook offers a balance between communicative and profession-oriented activities and lessons
- The activities encourage students to learn, communicate and participate both in usual everyday communication and professional contexts
- The grammar and vocabulary are introduced in realistic contexts, professional situations are also true-to-life
- The language usage is at the appropriated level of language and professional skills

Textbooks authors may use this checklist during their work; it may also be of use for teachers and students learning the language.

Discussions

The catalogues of Russian educational and library platforms contain a large number of textbooks on foreign language for future specialists in various fields (lawyers, civil servants, specialists in the field of tourism, economists, journalists, technologists, etc.), but there are no textbooks containing an indication of being written for future foreign language teachers in their title. An English language textbook for teachers (Krupchenko, Kuznetsov & Prilipko, 2020) was found in the *Youwrite* catalog, but, according to the authors, it is intended for teachers of all specialties and aims at “developing research competence among teachers” (Krupchenko, Kuznetsov & Prilipko, 2020, p. 7) and this specificity is clearly visible in both text and training materials.

The clarification that a particular manual is intended for students of language universities only indicates that its development implies a greater number of hours due to the depth of language learning, but not its professional focus. We have analyzed some manuals, which annotations indicated that their target audience is students of language schools, students of the "Linguistics" specialty (Abramova, 2020, Antonova, 2019, Pantyukhova & Reshetova, 2016). There we saw that despite a large number of effective exercises and tasks that provide thesaurus-based organization of knowledge (exercises for defining words, searching for synonyms, antonyms and collocations, studying their contextual use, etc.), these manuals do not convey the specifics of the future profession, do not offer models for applying the knowledge obtained in professional activities. Each of these manuals refers to the Federal State Educational Standard, lists the descriptors of the competencies stated in the standard, the analysis of which allows us to conclude that the need for professionalization of language training has not yet received sufficient recognition at the highest level.

Conclusion

Based on the above, we can conclude that at present there is an objective need for theoretical and practical understanding of the issue of linguists' language training professionalization.

The practical course of a foreign language in a pedagogical university has a huge potential, which can contribute to improving the level of future teachers' professional training.

The methodological basis of the new textbook should be a thesaurus-based approach. It can be implemented through the inclusion of not only specialty texts, but also tasks that ensure the thesaurus organization of knowledge and the formation of a pragmatic attitude to the process of learning a foreign language from the point of view of the future profession.

With this approach, the professional linguistic education of future foreign language teachers acquires new accents:

- the foreign language is regarded not only as an object of study, but also as a future subject of study (the student learns the language not only in order to be able to use it in various communicative situations, but also in order to later present it to his students);
- the language and speech material studied in the classes on the foreign language, the exercises done, the formulation of tasks, project activities are also considered from the point of view of the professional context..

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